

The Big-Five Personality Traits and Job Involvement among Secondary School Teachers in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Job involvement has emerged as an important outcome variable for many organizations and has drawn the attention of management scholars and organisational practitioners globally. In this study, the researcher examined personality traits as predictors of job involvement among secondary school teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. In a cross-sectional survey design, 354 teachers comprising of 195(55.1%) males and 159(44.9%) females within the age range of 22–62 years. Data were collected using the Teachers' Job Involvement Scale (TJIS) and the Big Five Inventory (BFI-44). Results from multiple linear regression analysis showed that personality traits jointly predicted overall job involvement with extraversion making the highest positive contribution followed by conscientiousness while neuroticism significantly contributed negatively to job involvement. Openness to experience and agreeableness however did not make any significant contribution. It was therefore, concluded that extraversion and conscientiousness are important traits required of a teacher to exhibit job involvement. Based on the findings, the study recommended that employers of teachers both in the private and public sectors should always apply personality screening test through trained occupational psychologists for the purpose of selection, placement and training.

Keywords: Big Five, Job involvement, Nigeria, Personality Traits, Secondary Schools, Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of job involvement has gained much popularity as an important variable in organisational research and has drawn the attention of management scholars and organisational practitioners globally. The enormous research attention given to job involvement is attributed to its association with many positive organisational outcomes including job satisfaction[1], job commitment[2], organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB)[3], superior in-role job performance[4], and employees' mental health and quality of life generally[5]. Thus, job involvement is considered an important outcome variable for many Nigerian organizations including the education sector.

Evidence exists that teachers with high level of job involvement often identify with teaching goals of the school more spontaneously, participate in teaching more eagerly and tend to produce good results in their professional life[6]. In Nigeria however, many public school teachers engage in practices indicating lack of job involvement such as absenteeism and or late coming to school and classes[7-8], inappropriate and non-keeping of records[9], trading within and outside school during working hours, commercial driving, immoral relationship with female students, and drinking and smoking during office hours[10],[11]. This lack of job involvement of teachers has been linked with the lack of seriousness, indiscipline and poor academic performance of students in schools[12], which have continued to be of concern to secondary school administrators, government, parents/ guardians and all other stakeholders in the education sector in Nigeria.

Generally, job involvement has been approached from two perspectives. The first perspective conceptualizes it as an individual difference variable which occurs when the possession of certain needs, values or personal characteristics

predispose individuals to become more or less involved in their jobs while the second perspective relates job involvement to a response to specific work situation or characteristics[13]. In line with the individual difference perspective, Barrick and Mount[14] proposed five factors of personality that most researchers continue to use today which represent the most significant personal viewpoints across measurements, cultures, and evaluations[15] and appear in various psychological fields, especially those pertaining to work performance[14]. The personality factors popularly known as the Big Five include openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism.

Openness to experience defines the extent to which an individual allows himself or herself to be affected by external or internal influences[15] and includes the ability to be imaginative, unconventional, curious, broadminded, and cultured[16]. Persons with higher levels of openness are more likely to achieve greater efficiency at work because they pursue opportunities to learn new perspectives and deal with ambiguous situations and are task-based, constantly searching for new methods to complete their work[17].

Conscientiousness is concerned with traits such as being diligent, attentive, vigilant, comprehensive, responsible, systematized and determined[14]. It also includes the characteristics of being persevering, organized, responsible, dependable, thorough and industrious. Individuals with this dimension are naturally hard working, result oriented, and ambitious which is why conscientious persons are linked with job satisfaction[18] and high job performance[14].

Extraversion on its part describes individuals who are expressive, outgoing, companionable, gregarious, chatty, confident, and determined[14]. Extroverts have a tendency to be spontaneous, communicative, energetic, positive, and enthusiastic[19],[20]. When compared with other five traits, extraverts are completely associated with emotional commitment[21] and are capable of practicing affirmative emotions[22] which in turn lead to job gratification[23].

Agreeableness is characterized by features such as self-sacrifice, helpfulness, nurturance, gentleness and emotional support at one end of the dimension, and enmity, indifference to others and self-interest on another end[24]. Agreeable individuals tend to be generous, calm, trusting, truthful, and sincere[25]. This personality dimension suggests a courteous, flexible, trusting, good-natured, cooperative, forgiving, soft-hearted, tolerant person[26]. Highly agreeable employees are likely to develop positive perceptions of work efficiency.

Neuroticism is defined as being emotionally insecure and uneven[15]. People dominant on this trait are often annoyed, stressed, sulky, unsociable, nervous, embarrassed, uncertain, doubtful, unconfident, fearful, and dejected[14],[25]. They have no belief and faith in others[19] and have no social expertise to handle the situations that claim to take control[27]. An employee dominant on neuroticism probably does not have positive attitudes towards work and may lack confidence and optimism, which should result in less ambition and less focus on career goals.

Many researchers[28]-[30], [18] have made various attempts at understanding the relationship between the Big Five personality traits and job involvement of different categories of employees. However, there exist inconsistencies in findings. For instance, Wood et al.[31] argued that introverts exhibit greater sensitivity to job involvement because they have lower pain threshold than extroverts while extroverts stand to drop on their commitment level which invariably decreases their level of job involvement. On the contrary, Thakre and Jadhav[32] reported that extraversion is rather positively related to job involvement; the relationship which Berg and Feij [33] attributed to the ability of extroverted employees to make better use of their competencies than do employees who are introverted. Apart from the inconsistency in findings which characterized research on the relationship between personality traits and job involvement, there is dearth of empirical literature within Nigeria bordering on the personality of teachers and their job involvement. This study is therefore designed to close this gap and further provide the knowledge which can be leveraged upon by policy makers, teachers and school administrators, parents, researchers and students of psychology, management and other related fields to bring about sustainable development in the Nigerian education sector.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Personality Traits and Job Involvement

Studies directly linking personality traits with job involvement are relatively scarce with research literature focusing more on similar constructs like employee engagement, job satisfaction and job commitment. Some of these studies are reviewed below. Rusdi and Tjahjono[34] investigated the effects of extraversion and agreeableness on job involvement. Data were collected from 190 registered nurses who worked at two public hospitals for additional research by employing PLS-SEM analysis. The findings show that extraversion, agreeableness, collectivism, and employee job involvement are all positively correlated. Herr et al.[35] in a three-wave study examined whether the pattern of associations of job demands and job

resources with work engagement and mental health depends on personality types using German workforce. The Big Five personality traits was used to cluster participants into five personality types: ordinary, resilient, strained, overcontrolled, and undercontrolled. Job demands were found to be associated with mental health while job resources were primarily associated with work engagement. However, these relationships differed across personality types. Although their research did not directly associate personality traits with job involvement, it is indicative of a similar relationship since work engagement and job involvement are similar constructs. Hamed et al.[36] conducted a study to determine the mediating role of job involvement in the relationship between personality traits and job performance among staff of Department of Education, NAJA and Tehran Municipality in which 400 people were selected by simple random sampling. The Job Performance Questionnaire, Job involvement Questionnaire and the Five-Factor Inventory were used for data collection. Among other findings, they reported significant direct effect of responsibility on employee job involvement while job involvement could not mediate in the relationship of extraversion, agreeableness and responsibility with job performance.

Khalid et al.[37] examined how dark triad traits affect depersonalization and job involvement via workplace incivility in the hospitality sector through the conservation of resources theory lens among 603 hotel employees in Greater Cairo. They found using the partial least squares (PLS) that dark triad traits positively and significantly predict workplace incivility while workplace incivility negatively affects job involvement and employee depersonalization. Fukuzaki and Iwata[38] in a meta-analysis examined the associations between work engagement and the five factor model of personality. They performed a database search for studies related to the research topic and 36 papers that reported correlation coefficients were selected. After correcting for publication bias using the trim-and-fill method, conscientiousness had the strongest positive association with work engagement, followed by extraversion, openness to experience and agreeableness while neuroticism and work engagement had negative association. Since work engagement and job involvement are similar organisational behaviours, it is safe to assume that personality traits have similar association with job involvement. On their part, Thakre and Jadhav[32] investigated the effect of extraversion on occupational stress, job involvement and job satisfaction using a sample of 120 salespersons working in the sales industry who were assessed with NEO-FFI, occupational stress index, job involvement scale and Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire. Findings of the study showed that extrovert sales employees reported less occupational stress, higher job involvement and satisfaction.

Abuelmhasen et al.[39] assessed the relationship between personality traits and organizational commitment of nursing staff of Elhawamdia General Hospital using a descriptive correlational design. Ninety (90) nursing staff selected through convenient sampling participated. The personality trait questionnaire and organizational commitment questionnaire were used for data collection. Findings revealed a statistically significant correlation between study nurses' personality traits and their organization commitment, which is a similar construct to job involvement. Mhlanga et al.[18] investigated the linear relationships and established usable models for the big five personality traits and psychological conditions on job engagement in a sample of 403 district municipal workers in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. They employed cross-sectional research design. Findings show that conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, intellect and all psychological conditions had a positive relationship with job engagement while neuroticism has a negative relationship with job engagement which is also a contextual performance like job involvement. Huang et al.[40] examined the effect of person-job fit on innovation behavior, highlighting the mediating role of job involvement and the moderating role of career commitment in this relationship. They tested their hypotheses using a sample of 474 employees from 30 IT enterprises in China's Pearl River Delta region. Findings revealed that person-job fit influences innovation behavior by enhancing job involvement. Janssens[41] conducted a study to enhancing insights into the relation between personality and engagement. Data were collected from 713 Flemish workers on their personality, work characteristics and engagement using validated questionnaires. Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to investigate the relation between personality traits and engagement. Results showed that both conscientiousness and extraversion were positively related to engagement and its three dimensions while higher levels of neuroticism were related to lower levels of vigor and dedication. Openness was negatively related to dedication while no relationship was found between agreeableness and engagement nor its dimensions.

Pallavi[42] assessed the level of job involvement of administrative employees at public sector undertaking and identified the predictors there of. Participants were 40 educated, experienced and mature members of administrative cadre. The questionnaire generated data on job involvement, two measures of personal attributes and ten dimensions of organizational climate. Regression analysis of the data identified personality traits as one critical predictor of job involvement. Shaban[43] examined the relationship between personality traits and employee engagement of public sector employees in Egypt. Findings from correlation and regression analysis showed that openness to experience had significant positive relationship with physical and emotional engagement, agreeableness was significantly related with emotional engagement, extroversion

and neuroticism had moderate and significant relationship with cognitive engagement. Farhangi et al.[44] studied the role of personality traits on job involvement with quality of work life as a mediator among staff members of a popular media organization in Tehran. The Five-factor Personality Questionnaire, Quality of Work Life Questionnaire and Kongo's Professional Attachment Questionnaire were used in getting data from 196 employees. Results of Pearson correlation demonstrated significant correlation between personality traits and quality of work life with job involvement. In addition, quality of work life significantly mediated the relationship between personality traits and job involvement.

Darbanyan et al.[28] investigated the relationship between the five-factor model of personality and job involvement among the employees of selected industrial corporations in Khorasan Razavi Province (Iran). The descriptive-correlational study included 150 randomly selected employees of the corporations. The NEO-FFI personality questionnaire (short version) and Kanungo's job involvement questionnaire were used for data collection. Results of Step-wise regression analysis showed that neuroticism and agreeableness negatively, openness to experience positively were able to predict job involvement. Okonkwo et al.[45] investigated the big five personality traits as predictors of job involvement among teachers. One hundred and seventeen (117) teachers comprising 31 males and 86 females were drawn from five government secondary schools in Enugu using Multi-stage sampling. The big five personality traits inventory and Lodahl and Wegner's 20-item job involvement scale were administered in a cross-sectional survey. Regression analysis revealed that extraversion, openness to experience and conscientiousness positively predicted job involvement while agreeableness and neuroticism did not.

B. Theoretical Framework

This study anchors on the Person–environment fit theory which is premised on the assumption that, stress arises not from the person or environment separately but rather by their fit or congruence with one another[46]. The theory assumes that every employee and organization each have separate specific behavioral traits and further proposed that the degree of congruence between an employee's trait or character and the organization's culture has a direct impact on employee satisfaction and company productivity. The higher the congruence, the higher the satisfaction and productivity while the lower the congruence, the lower the productivity and dissatisfaction[47]. When there is a good fit between employees and their organizations, employees take the initiative to engage in positive psychological constructs that change their perceptions of the organization or their jobs at a deeper level. In particular, if employees realize that there is a good fit between themselves and their workplace, which means that the organization is able to meet their needs and desires, they will have higher job involvement[40,48] and organizational commitment[49], better work attitude and greater identification with the organization[50]. Anchoring on the Person-Environment theory, this study proposes a significant relationship between the Big Five personality traits and job involvement of secondary school teachers in North-West Senatorial District of Benue State, Nigeria.

III. METHOD

A. Participants

The participants for this study were 354 teachers selected from 40 secondary schools in Benue State. They comprised 230(65%) selected from the public secondary schools and 124(35%) from private secondary schools. Their age range was between 22–62 years with mean age of 40.25 (SD=9.69). They were 195(55.1%) males and 169(44.9%) female who worked for at least 1 year, and 33 years maximum.

B. Instruments

The instruments for data collection comprised of two scales that measured the two major variables of the study – job involvement and Personality traits. *Job involvement* was measured with the Teachers' Job Involvement Scale (TJIS) which contained 29 items that measure two domains of teachers' job involvement: the physical and emotional involvement. Sample items include "I am determined to go extra miles for the sake of enhancing my teaching skills" and "Most of my interests are centered around my teaching job". The TJIS was developed and validated by the researcher due to lack of indigenous scales for measuring job involvement especially with the population of secondary school teachers. In a Principal Component Analysis using extraction method, two components were extracted with the first component loading 20 items and the other containing 9 items which represent the physical and emotional job involvement respectively. The two components explained 73.4% of the total variance observed in the scale. The scale exhibited high reliability with Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .97 for the entire scale while physical involvement had $\alpha=.94$ and emotional involvement had $\alpha=.70$. The scale showed good discriminant construct validity of $r=-.64$, when correlated with the classical alienation scale. *Personality traits* were assessed with the 44-item version of the Big Five Inventory[51]. The scale assesses personality from a five-dimensional

perspective: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness to experience. The authors established a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of .80 for the total scale while the Cronbach's alpha for the various subscales are: extraversion $\alpha=.37$, agreeableness $\alpha=.70$, conscientiousness $\alpha=.34$, neuroticism $\alpha=.40$, and openness to experience $\alpha=.70$. They found a convergent validity coefficient of .75 for the scale. In the present study, the BFI yielded an overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .95 while the subscales had Cronbach's alpha coefficients as follow: Openness to experience $\alpha=.85$; conscientiousness $\alpha=.85$; extraversion $\alpha=.67$; agreeableness $\alpha=.74$; and neuroticism $\alpha=.811$.

C. Procedure

For data collection, the researcher visited the participating schools personally. In selecting the schools that participated, the researcher first and foremost picked one-tenth (1/10) of the total number of schools in the study area. A sample of 40 schools was taken from the total of 396 secondary schools in North-West Senatorial District of Benue State, Nigeria. The 396 schools were first listed in alphabetical order. An interval was determined and an integer of 9 was also picked at random which was used in selecting every ninth school on the list. In sampling the teachers, the researcher used simple random sampling technique in which list of randomly generated numbers from the internet-based random number generator. The lists were generated according to the sample frame from each of the selected schools. The researcher recorded the total number of teachers from each of the sampled schools prior to data collection. This means that the total number of teachers from the 40 selected secondary schools was ascertained and their respective proportions in the sample size of 354 teachers also determined. The researcher collected data from teachers in each of the schools with the assistance of the school management.

D. Design/Statistics

This study employed the cross-sectional survey design. This involves collection of data from a relatively large number of participants at one point in time to make inferences about a population of interest. Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to analyze the data. The analysis was performed via the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Table 1: Multiple linear regression analysis showing personality traits and job involvement among secondary school teachers

DV	Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	Sig.	β	Sig.
Overall Job Involvement	Constant							.000
	Openness						-.046	.310
	Conscientiousness	.602	.362	5,348	39.51	.000	.389	.000
	Extraversion						.444	.000
	Agreeableness						-.072	.102
Physical Job Involvement	Neuroticism						-.173	.000
	Constant							.000
	Openness						.017	.724
	Conscientiousness	.511	.261	5,348	24.60	.000	.490	.000
	Extraversion						.139	.004
Emotional Job Involvement	Agreeableness						-.102	.033
	Neuroticism						-.101	.041
	Constant							.000
	Openness						-.091	.036
	Conscientiousness	.645	.416	5,348	49.56	.000	.203	.000
	Extraversion						.607	.000
	Agreeableness						-.028	.507
	Neuroticism						-.196	.000

Note: DV=Dependent Variable; JI=Overall Job Involvement; PJI=Physical Job Involvement; EJI=Emotional Job Involvement

Results showed that openness to experience ($\beta = -.046$, $p > .05$) did not significantly predict overall job involvement of secondary school teachers in Benue North-West Senatorial District in the same way it did not predict physical job involvement significantly ($\beta = .017$, $p > .05$). Openness to experience however predicted emotional job involvement negatively ($\beta = -.091$, $p < .05$) accounting for 9.1%, to emotional job involvement of the teachers. This means that teachers who are dominant on openness to experience as a personality trait are less likely to exhibit emotional job involvement.

The study further found that conscientiousness significantly predicted overall job involvement of the secondary school teachers positively ($\beta = .389$, $p < .01$) accounting for 38.9% of the total variance in the overall job involvement of secondary school teachers in Benue North-West Senatorial District of Benue State. Also, conscientiousness made significant positive contribution to physical job involvement ($\beta = .490$, $p < .01$) and emotional job involvement ($\beta = .203$, $p < .01$), accounting for 49% and 20.3% of the total variance in physical and emotional job involvement respectively. This means that teachers who are dominant on conscientiousness personality dimension have higher tendency to exhibit both physical and emotional job involvement. This further implies that conscientious teachers would be fully engaged and pre-occupied with their teaching job and the trait is a desired personality trait among secondary school teachers.

Further findings from the study indicate that extraversion made significant positive contribution to overall job involvement of secondary school teachers in North-West Senatorial District of Benue State ($\beta = .444$, $p < .01$), accounting for 44.4% of the total variance in overall job involvement. Also it was found that extraversion made significant positive contribution to physical job involvement ($\beta = .139$, $p < .01$) and emotional job involvement ($\beta = .607$, $p < .01$), accounting for 13.9% and 60.7% of the total variance in observed in physical and emotional job involvement respectively. This means that teachers dominant on extraversion as a personality trait have the tendency to exhibit high job involvement, especially the emotional dimension. This personality trait probably makes them to be happier in their workplace even in the face of daunting work challenges.

It was also found that agreeableness did not significantly predict overall job involvement ($\beta = -.072$, $p > .05$) of secondary school teachers in North-West Senatorial District of Benue State. Nevertheless, agreeableness significantly predicted physical job involvement negatively ($\beta = -.102$, $p < .05$) accounting for 10.2% of the total variance in physical job involvement of the teachers but did not significantly predict emotional job involvement of the secondary school teachers ($\beta = -.028$, $p > .05$). This means that teachers who are dominant on agreeableness personality trait can get physically involved in their job but on a whole, agreeableness personality trait is not a strong personality trait when it comes to job involvement among teachers. The fourth null hypothesis was not therefore, not rejected.

Findings from this study showed that neuroticism significantly predicted overall job involvement of secondary school teachers negatively ($\beta = -.173$, $p < .01$), accounting for 17.3% of the total variance observed in overall job involvement of the secondary school teachers. Neuroticism also made significant negative contribution to the prediction of physical job involvement ($\beta = -.101$, $p < .05$) and emotional job involvement ($\beta = -.196$, $p < .01$) accounting for 10.1% and 19.6% of the total variance observed in physical and emotional job involvement respectively among the secondary school teachers. This means that teachers who are dominant on neuroticism are less likely to exhibit job involvement both the physical and emotional dimensions. This implies that neuroticism as a personality trait is detrimental to job involvement of the teachers and those with this trait are by far, less likely to fully exhibit job involvement. This further indicates that this trait is an important factor in determining who is less likely to exhibit job involvement.

Finally, it was found that personality traits as a whole (viz: openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism) jointly predicted overall job involvement significantly among secondary school teachers in North-West Senatorial District of Benue State [$R = .602$, $R^2 = .362$, $F(5,348) = 39.512$, $p < .01$], accounting for 36.2% of the total variance observed in overall job involvement of the secondary school teachers. In terms of the two dimensions of job involvement, the results showed that personality traits jointly predicted physical job involvement [$R = .511$, $R^2 = .261$, $F(5,348) = 24.603$, $p < .01$] and emotional job involvement [$R = .645$, $R^2 = .416$, $F(5,348) = 49.560$, $p < .01$] significantly, accounting for 26.1% and 41.6% of the total variances observed in physical and emotional job involvement respectively. This result indicates that personality traits as a whole plays important role in the prediction of job involvement and its dimensions either positively or negatively as shown in the preceding part of the results. This means that personality traits can either enhance or lower job involvement of the secondary school teachers.

B. Discussions of the Findings

This study examined personality traits and job involvement among secondary school teachers in Benue State, Nigeria. Confirming the hypothesis, findings showed that personality traits have the ability to influence a teacher to be fully involved in the teaching job. This is in agreement with previous other researchers [35],[36],[39],[40],[42],[44] who in their separate studies identified personality traits as significant predictors of job involvement and its related concepts. Among the personality traits, extraversion and conscientiousness appeared as the most important predictors of both emotional and physical job involvement with ability to enhance both. This finding implies that teachers with extraverted personality are best suited for teaching job. This could be made possible by the blissful nature of their personality that makes them experience a contented life. Their positive attitude and energy are indeed important psychological resources that supply them with the strength to stay fully involved in their teaching job. Similarly, when the characteristics that make up conscientiousness personality trait are examined, one would eagerly affirm the validity of this finding. Characteristics such as perseverance, dependability, diligence and determination which define conscientiousness are positive psychological resources that are capable of strengthening a teacher's job involvement. This finding agrees with several other researchers [34],[38],[32],[41],[45] who found extraversion and conscientiousness as strong predictors of job involvement.

The findings also revealed that neuroticism is a significant negative predictor of both physical and emotional job involvement. What this finding means is that secondary school teachers who are dominant on neuroticism trait will be less involved in their teaching job. Neuroticism personality trait which is characterized by being emotionally insecure, easily stressed, uncertain and dejected, has the potential to make secondary school teachers less motivated and enthusiastic about their job. They can be easily stressed by slightest provocative stimuli in their environment. Teaching job being a task that requires high level of interaction among teachers, students, and parents, there is high likelihood that teachers who are dominant on neuroticism trait can easily find upsetting events that will stimulate negative emotions about their job therefore weakening their job involvement. This finding aligns with other researchers [37],[41],[28] who found similar negative association between neuroticism and job involvement. The finding however contradicts Okonkwo et al. [45] who found no significant relationship between neuroticism and job involvement.

Part of the findings is that openness to experience and agreeableness do not significantly predict job involvement of secondary school teachers. Although openness to experience and agreeableness seem to negatively influence emotional and physical job involvement respectively, they show no strong impact. This means that openness to experience and agreeableness have no direct link with job involvement of the teachers. They might be related to job involvement through other factors but not on their own as personality traits. As to openness to experience, it is not surprising that teachers who are open to experience would not significantly involve in their teaching job as shown by this study perhaps because of their curiosity, creativity and unconventional way of doing things which might not warrant them to enjoy the teaching job. This aspect of the finding is in line with other previous findings [41],[45] indicating no significant association between agreeableness and job involvement. It however disagrees with others [38],[43],[28] who found significant association between agreeableness, openness to experience and job involvement.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This study concludes that personality traits of the teachers, especially extraversion and conscientiousness are important traits required of a teacher to be involved in their job both physically and emotionally, whereas neuroticism, openness and agreeableness are not significant personality traits required of a teacher to guarantee their job involvement. The findings of this study have implications for both theory and practice. It has contributed in providing direction to organisational research literature on the role of personality traits in job involvement, particularly among secondary school teachers in Nigeria. Thus, the study has provided valuable knowledge that can be leveraged upon to enhance job involvement of teachers. Furthermore, the findings imply that personality traits are important factors in the management of performance of teachers. In order to enhance job involvement and professional practice of secondary school teachers, school administrators, both private and public, should consider personality traits as the basis for selecting the best candidates for teaching job in their institutions.

One of the limitations of this study is that the researcher relied solely on cross-sectional survey data which is quantitative and does not explore in-depth knowledge about a phenomenon. Secondly, the research was designed to cover the entire Benue State but in the actual study, only teachers in one out of the three senatorial zones in the state were sampled. Also, the researcher failed to compare public and private schools on job involvement but rather focused solely on the role of personality traits. Given the differences in style of administration and leadership, the results may not be the same for these two categories of schools.

Future studies should therefore adopt mixed method of data collection involving both surveys and interviews to gather data that will be richer in information about the variables under study. Further research should also consider a comparative analysis of job involvement between public and private secondary schools to understand the role of personality on job involvement between the two categories of school. They should as well, try to understand the mediating role of some situational factors such as leadership styles, organisational justice and organisational support in the relationship between personality traits and job involvement of teachers. Future studies should particularly focus on agreeableness and openness to experience which showed no direct relationship with job involvement of teachers in the present study.

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